

Clean milk production: a preventative approach for animal health

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Why produce clean milk?

1. To get milk with less bacteria
2. Prevention of diseases spread through unpasteurized milk
3. Good quality and good maintainability / longer life for good milk production
4. To increase the market price of milk
5. to milking in good dairies or companies
6. To ultimately make more profit

Sources of milk uncleanliness

(a) Internal

- Udder
- Starting stream of milk

(b) External source

- Animal self / animal skin / udder
- Milkman
- Utensil
- milking method
- Fodder, water etc.

Importance of clean milk production

- Milk production on a dairy farm is a major process on which the profits of a dairy farm depend.
- Due to regular cleanliness in the dairy farm located in the dairy farm, one keeps the udder of the animals healthy and the milk obtained from it also remains nutritious and usable for a long time.

Clean milk production has three main control points

- pertaining to the animal (cleanliness of the animal, especially the udder)
- Relating to the milkers (milking process, hand hygiene and personal hygiene/cleanliness)
- Environment related - Cleanliness of animal shed, Cleanliness of milk utensils, and Sanitation of animal's shed. Hence dairy owners (milkmen) should follow the following guidelines for clean milk production.

1. Animal shed cleaning

- The floor should be impervious and non-slippery.
- The milk shed should be thoroughly washed and dried after each milking so that the dairy remains clean and dry.

2. Animal cleaning

- The health of the animals should be checked regularly.
- The milking process of healthy animals should be done before the diseased animals so that healthy animals do not become diseased.
- If there is a lot of soil and dung on the back and thighs of the animal, then it should be cleaned with a brush and washed with water.
- Before milking, the udders should be wiped with a cloth dampened with antiseptic solution or the udders should be washed with this solution.

3. Cleaning of milk and milk utensils

- The milkers should wear clean clothes and cover his head with a suitable cap/cloth so that the hair of the head does not fall into the milk.
- The milkers' nails should be well cut and the hands should be cleaned with antiseptic solution after each milking.
- Couples with sick and dirty habits (eg: spitting here and there, making nose) should not be employed.

- After each use, the milk utensils should be washed first with warm water and then after rubbing thoroughly with suitable sanitizer (sanitizer) should be washed with cold water.
- Always use a sieve while pouring milk from one vessel to another.
- The first few squirts of milk from each udder should be collected in a strip-cup so that the milk can be tested for mastitis.

Milk quality test

- Milk is an important component of our diet. Certain standards have been made for the quality of milk used for human consumption.
- According to them, cow's milk should have 3.5 % fat and 8.5 % SNF and buffalo milk should have 5 % fat and 9 % SNF.
- To check the quality of milk, the following tests should be done at the milk collection centres.

(a) Test for colour, taste and smell

Colour- The colour changes due to the addition of any other substance in the milk. Unusual coloured milk is not suitable for human consumption.

Taste- The taste of milk should be normal. Milk of bitter or sour taste (cracked) usually we should not use.

Smell- The smell of milk should be normal.

(b) Testing of fat content in milk

- The fat content in milk is tested during the collection of milk.
- Generally, the traditional method is considered to test the fat content by the Gerber method, but recently electronic milk testers are being used in many parts of the country.
- Apart from fat, the remaining components of milk are collectively referred to as SNF and are determined by lactometer.

Due to fluctuation of fat and SNF in milk

Breed type

- Milk fat and SNF The quantity is inversely or seemingly related to the age of the animal.
- The animal suffering from any kind of disease or being frightened reduces the fat content in the milk.
- The fat content in milk increases from 15 days after calving to 9 months.
- The amount of fat increases even after moderate exercise.

To get remunerative price for the producers

- Milk should never be mixed in any way.
- During the measurement of milk quantity, milk should not be given to the institutions following the wrong procedure.
- According to the amount of fat present in the milk, the paying institution should supply the milk only.

Economics of milk production

- The profitability of a dairy enterprise depends upon the cost of milk production and the selling price of the milk.
- Although the producer has no control over the price of milk, he can control the cost of milk production.

To reduce the cost of milk production

- The cost of milk production can be reduced to a great extent by cultivating green fodder on own land.
- Contribution of family members should be encouraged instead of outside labor for various functions of dairy operation.
- The calving should match the period of availability of green fodder.
- The animal which is in the fourth or fifth statement, more attention should be paid to their rearing.
- Control unreasonable expenditure on green fodder, oilseeds, cereals and medicines.

Cause of milk adulteration

- Milk naturally contains high quality nutrients. For this reason, people try to earn more money by adulteration of other food items of low quality in milk.

Examples of adulteration

- Dalda, refined and vegetable oils are added to increase the fat content.
- Sugar, maida, flour, urea, salt etc. are added to increase the snf.
- Water is added to milk to increase the quantity of milk.
- Removal of fat/fat from milk.

Measures to maintain the quality of milk

- The farmer should produce milk in clean conditions.
- Clean utensils should be used for milk production.
- The milk should be cooled to 5°C as soon as possible.
- In this way the cold milk should be sent for processing.
- After this the milk should be pasteurized and cooled. Such milk should be packed and sent to the consumer.